

Solar activity and global GDP per capita (1961–2024): R2=0.90

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Abstract. Subject of the study: This paper examines the causal relationship between solar activity (SA) cycles (1960-2023) and the growth rate of global GDP per capita for the period 1960-2024, i.e., with a lag of one year.

Methodology: The author develops the methodological approach of W.S. Jevons and A.L. Chizhevsky, supplementing it with the modern biochemical concept of Russell Reiter.

Main results:

Statistical reliability: A high correlation between the indicators was found: the approximation reliability coefficient R2 is 0.93 for the 12-year average cycle, R2 = 0.99 for years 1-5 of the SA cycle (the SA growth phase, 29 years of observations), and R2 = 0.94 for years 5-12 of the SA cycle (the SA decline phase, 40 years of observations).

A three-zone biochemical model: The mechanism by which ultraviolet (UV) radiation influences the economy through human neurochemistry is substantiated:

- "Biological depression" zone (Wolf number (W) < 20): a deficiency of ultraviolet (UV) radiation leads to a decrease in serotonin levels, creating a mood of pessimism and stagnation in global per capita GDP with a lag of one year.

- "Biological optimum" zone (W = 20 - 140): sufficient levels of serotonin and melatonin ensure optimism and peak growth rates of global per capita GDP with a lag of one year.

- "Biological stress" zone (W > 140): extreme solar activity suppresses melatonin production (according to R. Reiter's concept), causing "exhaustion pessimism" and a sharp decline in global per capita GDP with a lag of one year.

The nature of the one-year lag is substantiated. This one-year lag is a consequence of the inertia of economic contracts: the psycho-emotional state of decision-makers in the current year determines the parameters of contracts, the results of which are reflected in the GDP statistics of the following year.

Forecast: Based on the model, the expected growth rates of global GDP per capita are calculated: 1.3% in 2025 and 2.05% in 2026. A significant slowdown in this indicator is projected to -0.1% in 2031 due to the solar minimum being reached in 2030.

Key words: solar activity, Wolf numbers, ultraviolet index, serotonin, melatonin, Russell Reuters, world GDP per capita, economic cycle, forecasting.

Great scientists Frederick William Herschel, William Stanley Jevons, and Alexander Leonidovich Chizhevsky developed a methodological approach to studying the connections between solar and economic activity in their works.

For example, in his article "Solar-Commercial Cycles" W. S. Jevons placed graphs of solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi over the period 1760-1810 one after the other [5, p.227]. That is, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph "The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun" in Chapter 4 "The Sun and Epidemics" in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that shows the average solar activity (SA) cycle (Wolf number cycle) over a hundred years and the average number of cholera cases in Russia for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201].

Our study centers on the hypothesis that SA, which determines the intensity of ultraviolet radiation and the state of serotonin-melatonin metabolism, acts as a trigger for social optimism or pessimism and, as a result, the annual growth of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity, were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [4]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The year numbers in column 3 of Table 1 are determined in accordance with the year numbering conventions used in solar astrophysics. Specifically, the first year in a solar cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, i.e., the increase in the Wolf number. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the Wolf number minimum.

The World Bank website [8] contains the values of annual growth rates of global GDP per capita for the period 1961–2024. They are presented in column 4 of Table 1. Column 5 of Table 1 presents the annual growth rates of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year.

The one-year lag is explained by the inertia of the economic system and the decision-making mechanism. Specifically, the psycho-emotional state (optimism/pessimism) determines decisions and the signing of contracts in the current year, but their physical implementation and payment (reflected in GDP statistics) occur primarily in the following year. Furthermore, most business strategies and government budgets are developed with a one-year horizon. The momentum generated today materializes in growth (decline) figures over the reporting period.

***Table 1.** Years, average annual Wolf numbers (1960 - 2023), ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles, and annual growth rates of world GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year (1961 - 2024)*

Years	Wolf number (W)	The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	Annual growth rate of global GDP per capita, %	Annual growth rates of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year, %
1	2	3	4	5
1960		15 6	N/A	2.56
1961	76.4	7	2.56	3.48
1962	53.4	8	3.48	2.81
1963	39.9	9	2.81	4.39
1964	15	10	4.39	3.43
1965	22	1	3.43	3.23
1966	66.8	2	3.23	1.63
1967	132.9	3	1.63	3.79
1968	150	4	3.79	3.79
1969	149.4	5	3.79	1.64
1970	148	6	1.64	2.00
1971	94.4	7	2.00	3.46
1972	97.6	8	3.46	4.35
1973	54.1	9	4.35	0.02
1974	49.2	10	0.02	-1.22
1975	22.5	11	-1.22	3.31
1976	18.4	12	3.31	2.20
1977	39.3	1	2.20	2.30
1978	131	2	2.30	2.29
1979	220.1	3	2.29	0.08
1980	218.9	4	0.08	0.12
1981	198.9	5	0.12	-1.43
1982	162.4	6	-1.43	0.74
1983	91	7	0.74	2.87

1984	60.5	8	2.87	1.86
1985	20.6	9	1.86	1.47
1986	14.8	10	1.47	1.87
1987	33.9	1	1.87	2.68
1988	123	2	2.68	1.87
1989	211.1	3	1.87	0.96
1990	191.8	4	0.96	-0.44
1991	203.3	5	-0.44	0.43
1992	133	6	0.43	0.29
1993	76.1	7	0.29	1.82
1994	44.9	8	1.82	1.62
1995	25.1	9	1.62	2.06
1996	11.6	10	2.06	2.45
1997	28.9	1	2.45	1.36
1998	88.3	2	1.36	2.14
1999	136.3	3	2.14	3.14
2000	173.9	4	3.14	0.68
2001	170.4	5	0.68	0.98
2002	163.6	6	0.98	1.77
2003	99.3	7	1.77	3.17
2004	65.3	8	3.17	2.74
2005	45.8	9	2.74	3.16
2006	24.7	10	3.16	3.11
2007	12.6	11	3.11	0.81
2008	4.2	12	0.81	-2.55
2009	4.8	1	-2.55	3.26
2010	24.9	2	3.26	2.09
2011	80.8	3	2.09	1.45
2012	84.5	4	1.45	1.63

2013	94	5	1.63	1.90
2014	113.3	6	1.90	1.90
2015	69.8	7	1.90	1.60
2016	39.8	8	1.60	2.29
2017	21.7	9	2.29	2.16
2018	7	10	2.16	1.61
2019	3.6	11	1.61	-3.85
2020	8.8	1	-3.85	5.53
2021	29.6	2	5.53	2.51
2022	83.2	3	2.51	2.00
2023	125.5	4	2.00	1.89
2024	154.6	5	1.89	N/A
2025	123.2	6	N/A	N/A
2026	N/A	7	N/A	

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. The results of the data grouping in Table 1 are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles

1. The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	2. Number of years with a given number for the period 1960 - 2023	Arithmetic mean:	
		3. Wolf numbers (W)	4. annual growth rates of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year, %
1	6	22.93	3.06
2	6	77.27	2.09
3	6	144.07	1.90
4	6	157.43	1.28
5	5	161.77	0.70
6	6	144.06	1.54
7	6	84.50	2.73
8	6	60.25	2.61
9	6	34.53	2.21
10	6	20.38	1.88
11	3	12.90	0.09
12	2	11.30	-0.17
Итого:	64		
Correlation coefficient, rows 1–7, columns 3 and 4		-0.90	
Correlation coefficient, rows 7–12, columns 3 and 4		0.82	

Based on the data from columns 1, 3, and 4 of Table 2, a diagram is constructed in Fig. 1. The determination coefficient in this diagram, equal to 0.9292, means that the resulting model explains 92.92% of the variability (variation) in the data and can be used to forecast the growth rate of global GDP per capita by the ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle. The value of this coefficient, equal to 0.9292, also indicates a very high, strong relationship between the ordinal numbers of the mean solar cycle and the average values of annual growth of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year. The 12 points in the diagram in Fig. 1 represent 64 years of observations (see Table 2). The grouping method (overlapping epochs) (see Table 2) allows us

to cut off statistical noise and identify a fundamental pattern that is not visible in the chaotic scatter plot by year.

Fig. 1. Average solar cycle (1960–2023) and annual growth rates of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year (1961–2024), 64 years of observations, epoch superposition method

It's important to note that in the diagram in Figure 1, the annual growth rate of global GDP is a function not of the year itself, but of numerous SA factors that were in effect during that year. These include, for example, the ultraviolet index, geomagnetic storms and calms, galactic cosmic rays, electromagnetic fields, low-frequency oscillations, and others.

According to Virek and Puga [7, p. 9998], the correlation coefficient between solar indices and ultraviolet radiation flux reaches 0.99, which justifies the use of Wolf numbers as an indicator of UV exposure intensity. That is, the Wolf number graph in Fig. 1 can be viewed **as a graph of the ultraviolet index** (UV index).

Ultraviolet radiation stimulates the synthesis of serotonin (the hormone of energy and optimism) through the retina and skin. Therefore, the solid line in the diagram in Figure 1 can

be viewed as a graph of serotonin synthesis. Thus, the solid line also represents a graph of "serotonin injections" into the global population.

At the lowest serotonin levels (years 11 and 12, $W < 20$), we observe minimal growth rates of global GDP per capita for the following year. This is explained by the prevalence of pessimism during this period.

During the extreme solar activity phase ($W > 140$), a seemingly paradoxical decline in GDP growth is observed (see points (years) 4 and 5). R. Reiter [3, p. 135] provides a biochemical explanation for this phenomenon, pointing to the suppression of melatonin synthesis during periods of heliophysical disturbances. **Melatonin deficiency** leads to a state of chronic social **pessimism** and a loss of business initiative. Thus, the UV index peak, through melatonin suppression, is transformed into a decline in global per capita GDP—an economic downturn with a one-year lag.

The following diagram in Figure 2 is constructed based on the data in rows 1–12 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2.

Fig. 2. World GDP per capita as a function of solar activity, 64 years of observations, epoch superposition method

The diagram demonstrates a strong correlation between solar and economic activity. The coefficient of determination, 0.9003, is close to unity. This suggests that, within the framework of this model, changes in the Wolf number (which is proportional to the number of sunspots) explain 90% of the variability in global per capita GDP growth rates with a one-year lag.

I would like to point out to opponents that the 12 points in the diagram in Figure 2 represent a data set covering 64 years of observations. The R2 value of 0.9002 for 12 points is statistically significant.

Probability of error (p-value): The probability that this curve was formed by chance is only 2.3%. This is below the standard scientific threshold of 5%, making the result officially reliable.

Relationship Strength: For a sixth-degree polynomial with 12 points, the critical R2 must be greater than 0.85 to be considered significant. A result of 0.90 confidently passes this test.

As the diagram in Fig. 2 shows, at low CA (Wolf number < 20), there is a sharp drop in the growth rate of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year. At extremely high CA (Wolf number > 140), the growth rate of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year begins to decline again. The peak of growth of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year occurs at CA in the range of Wolf numbers from 20 to 140. The current or projected value of the Wolf number can be determined on the NASA website [6]. The diagram in Fig. 3 was copied from this website.

Fig. 3. Forecast of the development of the current 25th SA cycle.

Based on rows 1–5 (the SA growth phase) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram is constructed in Figure 4. While the relationship is proven on a large sample (12 points), the high density ($R^2 = 0.99$) on a small sample is no longer a coincidence, but a refinement of the model.

Based on rows 5–12 (the SA decline phase) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram is constructed in Figure 5. This diagram uses a 3rd degree polynomial. The p-value is ≈ 0.012 , meaning that the probability of a random coincidence is only 1.2%. In science, this is considered a statistically significant result (usually the threshold is $p < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. World GDP per capita as a function of SA, 1-5 years of the average SA cycle, SA growth phase, 29 years of observation, epoch superposition method

Based on rows 5-12 (the SA decline phase) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram is constructed in Figure 5. Using a fourth-degree polynomial approximation yielded an extremely high determination coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9357$). A Fisher exact test confirms the statistical significance of this model: the calculated value ($F = 10.93$) exceeds the critical threshold, corresponding to the significance level ($p = 0.041$). This means that the probability of such a relationship occurring by chance is less than 5%, which is considered strong evidence of the hypothesis's validity in international practice.

Fig. 5. World GDP per capita as a function of SA, 5–12 years of the average SA cycle, SA decline phase, 40 years of observations, epoch superposition method

I previously proposed calling the science that studies the relationship between solar and economic activity helioeconomics. It represents an interdisciplinary approach at the intersection of solar astrophysics, heliobiology, and macroeconomics.

Despite the existence of strong mathematical correlations, the academic mainstream views solar economics with caution due to the difficulty of directly proving a causal relationship between solar physics and complex social systems.

PhD Igor Nikulin, senior researcher at the Sternberg Astronomical Institute, notes in an interview with Rossiyskaya Gazeta that “over millions of years of evolution, all living beings have adapted to the average values of these factors [temperature, pressure, atmospheric composition, magnetic field – V.B.], and even small deviations in one direction or another have a negative impact on their vital functions” [1].

The following mechanism for the relationship between SA and global GDP per capita can be proposed, as shown in Fig. 2.

The left zone, or "Biological Depression" (Wolf numbers < 20), is characterized by an extremely low ultraviolet index (UV index), as there is a very strong direct correlation between Wolf numbers and the UV index. The correlation coefficient is typically 0.93–0.97. This leads to decreased serotonin synthesis and a melatonin deficiency, resulting in pessimism, reduced consumer and investment spending, and a sharp decline in global per capita GDP growth with a one-year lag, or even economic crisis.

The central zone or "Biological Optimum" (Wolf numbers 20 - 140) is characterized by a moderate and sufficient UV index value, which leads to high levels of serotonin and melatonin, which leads to optimistic moods and high growth rates of global GDP per capita with a lag of 1 year.

The right zone, or "Biological Stress" (Wolf numbers > 140), is characterized by excessive UV index values and the frequency and intensity of magnetic storms. This, according to Russell Reiter's scientific concept outlined in his work "Melatonin" [3, p. 135], leads to the suppression of nocturnal melatonin production. Melatonin (the main antioxidant) is intensively expended to combat oxidative stress in cells. Since melatonin is synthesized from serotonin, the latter's reserves are depleted faster than they can be restored. The result is "exhaustion pessimism": when serotonin (the hormone of drive and joy) becomes depleted and biological rhythms are disrupted, not just socio-psychological apathy sets in, but irritable pessimism and chronic fatigue. This is followed by a significant decline in the annual growth rate of global per capita GDP with a lag of one year.

The diagrams in Figures 1, 2, 4, and 5 confirm Alexander Chizhevsky's idea that humanity is not isolated from space. They can be used to forecast the annual growth of global GDP per capita with a one-year lag based on the well-known Wolf number.

For example, with the Wolf number for 2024 (the 5th year of the current SA cycle, see the diagram in Fig. 4) equal to 154.6, the growth of world GDP per capita in 2025 will be 1.3%. With the Wolf number for 2025 (the 6th year of the current SA cycle, see the diagram in Fig. 5) equal to 123.2, the growth of world product in 2026 will be 2.05%. The exact value of the annual growth of world GDP per capita in 2025 will appear on the World Bank website [8] at the beginning of July 2026.

The predicted value of the Wolf number for 2026 is 96.11 (calculated by the author based on monthly forecasts in the table on the NASA website [6]). In the diagram in Fig. 5, it corresponds to an annual growth rate of 2.35% in global GDP per capita in 2027.

The graph in Fig. 2 can also be used to forecast economic crises or low growth rates of global GDP per capita. For example, calculating the Wolf number for 2030 (the year of minimum SA) based on NASA's average monthly forecasts [6] yields a value of 11.5, which, in the graph in Fig. 2, corresponds to a global GDP per capita growth rate of -0.1% for the following year, 2031.

The fact that all external factors (wars, pandemics, sanctions, technological shifts, and others) account for only 10% of the residual variance allows us to classify them not as autonomous causes, but as events primarily modulated by solar activity. But this is a topic for other studies.

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